

Agro2Circular

D3.14 – Technologies for sorting and recycling of multilayer plastics residues

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List of abbreviations

GWC:	Green World Compounding
CETEC:	Technological Center for Footwear and Plastics
PE:	Polyethylene
PP:	Polypropylene
DPP:	Digital Product Passport
PHA:	Polyhydroxyalkanoates
WP6:	Work Package 6
A2C	Agro2Circular
EG	Ethylene Glycol
PIB	Polyisobutylene
NIAS	Non-Intentionally Added Substances
NIR-HIS	Near Infrared – Hyperspectral Imaging
PET	Polyethylene Terephthalate
LDPE	Low-Density Polyethylene
PA	Polyamide
EVOH	Ethylene Vinyl Alcohol
DSC	Differential Scanning Calorimetry
FT-IR	Fourier-Transform Infrared Spectroscopy
TGA	Thermogravimetric Analysis
HDPE	High-Density Polyethylene
H₂O₂	Hydrogen Peroxide
CO₂	Carbon Dioxide
LIBS	Laser-Induced Breakdown Spectroscopy
FAT	Factory Acetoce Text
APTES	(3-aminopropyl)ethoxysilane

1 Executive summary <abstract>

The plastic waste generated in the agri-food and agricultural sectors presents significant technical challenges. Its multi-layered nature combines different plastic materials and is often contaminated with agrochemicals and organic waste. These factors make the application of conventional recycling methods difficult.

Due to their complex composition, these plastic wastes require advanced technologies that allow for efficient separation and proper decontamination. This process ensures the removal of contaminations such as agrochemicals, soil, and organic matter, enabling the effective reuse of the materials.

In this context, various treatment technologies in line have been researched and developed to recover and transform the plastic waste fractions into valuable raw materials. The goal is to obtain high-value-added recycled products, such as non-aluminized plastic fractions, modified aluminium, alkanes, EG (ethylene glycol), TPA (terephthalic acid), and organic by-products. These materials will be used to create new compatibilized synthetic polymers, biodegradable polymers, as well as to develop end products for cosmetic applications and other industries, through the demonstration of the A2C Technological Solution, which will be carried out in Work Package 6.

To achieve this goal, a line for shredding, cleaning, and drying plastic materials has been developed, allowing the production of a small size clean fraction ready to be classified. This process includes an optical sorting stage that distinguishes between fractions containing aluminium and those that do not. The fractions are then processed differently:

1. Fraction with aluminium: This fraction undergoes a delamination process to separate the aluminium from plastics. Then, an enzymatic modification is performed on the plastics present to obtain their monomers, optimizing their upcycling and enabling valorisation. Furthermore, the aluminium removed from the plastic fractions is modified to improve the compatibility with the plastic matrix and therefore, improved properties in films for specific applications.

2. Fraction without aluminium: This fraction is subjected to a compatibilization process, where compatibilizers are added to improve the mix between the different types of polymers. This allows for the production of compatibilized synthetic plastics that are recycled and recyclable, with enhanced properties that can be used in various industrial applications, from packaging to everyday plastic products.

This innovative solution will significantly contribute to the reduction of plastic waste while promoting the recovery of valuable materials and improving sustainability in industrial processes. In addition to this, it is worth highlighting that an example of this is the organic by-products recovery and microplastic removal, where organic matter recovered from wastewater treatment could potentially be used to obtain PHA (Polyhydroxyalkanoates). However, the concentration of organic matter at this point may not yet be high enough, as it depends on the plastics and particularly on how 'fresh' the organic matter is. This is an area that we hope to explore further in WP6.

2 Introduction

Plastic recycling remains one of the most significant challenges in the search for sustainable solutions for waste management. In particular, multi-layer aseptic bags used as packaging in the liquid food industry and agricultural disinfection films, which are materials made up of several layers of different polymers and, in some cases, metals like aluminium. These combinations make recycling extremely complex, as the materials must be properly separated before they can be reused. Within the framework of the Agro2Circular project, innovative separation technologies have been developed and tested for these multi-layer plastics.

This report provides a detailed description of the most relevant advancements achieved in the various phases of the project, including innovative technologies for material separation, the improvement of recycled plastic properties, and biological processes that allow the transformation of certain polymers into valuable components for the production of other relevant products in the industry.

3 KEY ADVANCEMENTS IN THE RECYCLING OF COMPLEX MATERIALS

Within the framework of the Agro2Circular (A2C) project, innovative processes have been developed to recover key materials: non-aluminized plastic fractions, modified aluminium, alkanes, ethylene glycol (EG), and terephthalic acid (TPA).

These advancements include conditioning technologies, optical sorting, delamination, decontamination, chemical modification of aluminium, enzymatic modification, and the transformation of plastic compounds.

3.1 ADVANCES IN PLASTIC WASTE CONDITIONING

The process begins with a comprehensive pre-treatment, where the plastic material undergoes shredding, washing, and centrifugation. This initial conditioning results in smaller and cleaner plastic fragments, facilitating the subsequent recycling stages.

In the case of agricultural plastics, such as disinfection films used to protect soils, the additional challenge lies in contamination with pesticide residues and chemicals applied during use. This contamination poses potential risks to human health and the environment, making its treatment a key priority within the Agro2Circular project.

To address these challenges, advanced processes have been implemented, such as two-stage milling and multiple counter-current washes, which increase the friction between the cleaning fluid and the plastic material. The material is then dried and subjected to vacuum extrusion, where residual contaminants are effectively removed through vapor extraction. During this stage, a vacuum chamber ensures that the calcined residues from high temperatures, which were not eliminated during the vapor extraction, do not react with each other, preventing the presence of substances that could contribute to the contamination of the material.

Figure 1. Process Flowchart corresponding to the washing line where the trial of grinding and washing agricultural disinfection film waste was carried out.

In addition, advanced Refreshing Processes (post-extrusion treatments) have been implemented, achieving a deeper removal of contaminants without compromising the quality of the recycled plastics. These processes use steam at 100°C as a decontamination agent, providing highly effective additional cleaning. This aspect will be discussed in more detail in section 3.2.

Figure 2. Activities involved in the valorisation of agricultural disinfection mulch (A2C solution)

In the case of multi-layer aseptic bags, the process is similar, including shredding, counter-current washing, and centrifugation, which allows for the production of small, clean, and dry multi-layer fragments. Since the waste comes from the food industry, the material's usage conditions are less aggressive compared to agricultural plastics. Therefore, it is considered that the extrusion process, following optical sorting and detailed later in section 3.2, is sufficient to ensure decontamination, without the need for a subsequent refreshing process, as is the case with agricultural waste. However, it is essential to perform an analysis of the NIAS (non-intentionally added substances) in the final product (WP6 “A2C demonstrators”), as validation processes such as transport, storage, conditioning, waste sorting, and high-temperature extrusion could influence the presence of potential contaminants.

Figure 3. Process Flowchart corresponding to the washing line where the trial of grinding of washing multilayer aseptic plastic bag waste was carried out.

Figure 4. Activities involved in the valorisation of multilayer aseptic plastic bag waste (A2C solution)

3.2. ADVANCEMENTS IN THE DECONTAMINATION OF RECYCLED PLASTIC

Since the plastic waste described in section 3.1 comes from its use in agriculture, where it is exposed to pesticide application, there is concern about the presence of hazardous chemical residues in the materials. These residues may contain substances potentially harmful to human health and the environment.

In the first hypothesis of the process, it is assumed that both washing and extrusion play a key role in eliminating a significant portion of these contaminants.

Figure 5 Erema TVEPlus Extruder machine in GWC Agricultural mulch film waste recycling plant

The washing process is effective in removing the most superficial and accessible residues from the material, while extrusion, in particular, helps prevent certain calcined contaminants or chemical residues from reacting and forming new hazardous compounds. Degassing in the extrusion process is carried out in two key stages: the preheating and pre-drying of the material.

Figure 6 Different parts of the final decontamination process undergone by grinded and washed plastics in the Intarema TVEPlus Extruder

- The feeding process is fully automatic and ensuring consistent and efficient material input. (1).
- In the preconditioning unit, the material is mixed, heated, dried, pre-compacted, and buffered (2). During this stage, gas extraction takes place, which allows the volatilization of surface contaminants, contributing to early-stage decontamination. This process improves the overall cleanliness of the material, reduces the load of contaminants entering the extruder
- Inside the extruder screw, the material is plasticized and undergoes reverse degassing, helping to reduce the gas load in the subsequent stages (3). This step ensures better melt quality by removing entrapped gases early on
- At the end of the plasticising zone the melt is directed out of the extruder, cleaned in the fully automatic, self-cleaning filter (4) and returned to the extruder again
- The final homogenisation of the melt (5) takes place after the melt filter. This step improves the consistency of the polymer melt by evenly distributing temperature and material composition, which enhances the mechanical properties and performance of the final product.
- In the following degassing zone, the filtered and homogenized melt is thoroughly degassed to remove remaining volatile components or gas inclusions (6). This stage prevents defects such as bubbles or voids in the final material, reduces the risk of contamination, and improves the overall purity and safety of the recycled polymer.
- The melt is conveyed under extremely low pressure to the next processing step (7). Operating at low pressure helps preserve the polymer's quality by minimizing shear stress and avoiding the reintroduction of gases or contaminants.
- Finally, the melt is directed to the appropriate tool, such as a pelletizer, for final shaping or form conversion (8).

In addition to these processes, advanced Refreshing technologies (post-extrusion treatments) have been implemented, which have proven effective in the deep removal of contaminants without compromising the quality of the recycled plastics. These treatments use steam at 100°C as a decontamination agent, providing highly effective additional cleaning.

In an initial analysis, the presence of chlorine and sulfur was evaluated to verify the removal of pesticide residues in the materials. While the results showed a reduction in the levels of these compounds, it was not as significant as expected, and unfortunately, a complete removal could not be guaranteed. Therefore, to determine whether the presence of these elements is related to the emergence of Non-Intentionally Added Substances (NIAS) or whether they are due to the persistence of complete pesticide molecules or disinfection compounds, a more thorough analysis was carried out. This analysis included the detection of over 500 pesticides at various stages of the process.

Samples were taken from shredded plastic, washed and dried flakes and pellets, as well as from the vacuum condensates generated by the extruder and the washing water, both before and after flocculation treatments.

The results show that although the shredded material and final pellets do not contain pesticides as identifiable substances, significant amounts of certain compounds were detected in the washed and dried plastic flakes, in the washing water (both dirty and treated after flocculation), and in the vacuum condensates from the extrusion process. This uneven distribution of contaminants suggests that pesticide accumulation occurs within the system. However, the extrusion process has proven effective in breaking down these compounds, as no traces are identified in the final product.

Nevertheless, the presence of these compounds in earlier stages raises the possibility of NIAS (Non-Intentionally Added Substances) formation. Although it has been demonstrated that pesticide residues are eliminated by the extrusion process, it can also be reasoned that any NIAS formed in previous stages may have been removed during extrusion. This will be verified through the demonstrators to be carried out in WP6.

3.3. ADVANCEMENTS IN OPTICAL SORTING PROCESS

Up to date, all the efforts from IRIS within Task 3.2 have been focused on prioritizing the fact of sorting (optically and mechanically) the metallised fractions integrated in the plastics multilayer materials in order to obtain two different streams (one with plastics and another one with metallised plastic materials). Some relevant techniques for the discrimination of the

metallised fractions within plastic aseptic bags were studied during the first part of the project (NIR-HSI, Laser induced breakdown spectroscopy -LIBS- and the use of a metal detector). After the observation of the results and after analysing the samples through the mentioned techniques, the most promising technique that would showcase technical feasibility in an industrial environment is NIR-HSI. Some challenges with overlapping and sorting typical of light, flexible and small size samples have been tackled in the last months. As well, the size of the grinding required for the implementation of the sorting device was optimized and some feeding speed tests were carried out. At this stage, the specifications of the optical sorting prototype have been established, the design of the equipment has been carried out and the prototype is being developed, including the mechanical, electric, electronical, software, automation and optical systems.

The next steps will be to carry out the Factory Acceptance Tests (FAT), which will be performed to guarantee that the components are running properly and the monitoring and sorting systems have a good performance in an industrial environment. Finally, a pilot scale-up will be taking place in order to evaluate the performance of the prototype in a real environment (at GWC facilities), coupling the monitoring and sorting unit with other processes. This work will be done in the framework of task 6.1 “Integration of the technologies at pilot scale”.

3.4. ADVANCEMENTS IN PLASTIC FRACTION DELAMINATION

The aluminized fractions described in this section, obtained through optical sorting, originate from complex structures widely used in the packaging industry, such as barrier-laminates with aluminium-metallization or aluminium sheets. These materials present unique recycling challenges due to the need for effective separation of their components to maximize the purity of recovered materials and ensure their efficient reuse.

Saperatec's technology leverages specially designed separation fluids that enable the delamination of these composites, separating aluminium and polymers. Below are the achievements and limitations identified so far.

Results Achieved:

- Laminates with aluminium-metallization and aluminium sheets were successfully delaminated, separating PE, PET, and aluminium fractions effectively.
- In the case of laminates with aluminium sheets, aluminium was recovered alongside plastics, improving recycling efficiency and reducing CO₂ footprint.
- The separation fluid proved reusable across multiple delamination cycles without loss of efficacy.
- The delamination and separation process was validated at a pilot scale, achieving good results in sorting materials with significant density differences (e.g., PE and PET).
- Recovered materials, including PE, PET and aluminium, retained high quality and purity after treatment with the separation fluid.

Limitations and Next Steps:

- Separating materials with close densities (e.g., PE and PET/PE) requires further development and optimization.
- The existing pilot equipment cannot be transported due to its size and complexity, necessitating the design of a demonstrator tailored to the project's requirements.

3.5. PLASTIC PROCESSABLE COMPOUNDS

The development of processable compounds using recycled plastics derived from aseptic bags and multilayer agricultural films has been successfully carried out.

To validate the procedure, polymer blends such as LDPE, PA, and EVOH were mixed with compatibilizers in various concentrations. These blends were subsequently subjected to

detailed evaluations to analyse their performance and compatibility. The process included key stages such as extrusion, calendering, and thermal, mechanical, and structural characterization of the blends. The results demonstrated significant advancements in optimizing compatibilizers and improving the final properties of recycled materials. However, challenges remain in achieving complete integration of the polymers, which must be addressed in pilot-scale industrial tests.

A significant milestone was the successful production of 40-micron films via calendering, using compatibilizers in industrially realistic proportions (3% to 5%). Additionally, the characterization of the blends, carried out through techniques such as DSC, FT-IR, and TGA, provided crucial data on the thermal stability and compatibility of the developed materials.

Results Achieved:

- **Improved Compatibility:** Partial compatibility was achieved between immiscible polymers through the use of compatibilizers, enhancing mechanical properties in some blends.
- **Interaction Mechanisms Identified:** Key mechanisms of interaction between compatibilizers and polymers were identified, though conclusive evidence was lacking in some cases.

Limitations and Next Steps:

- **Persistent Immiscibility:** LDPE, PA, and EVOH showed immiscibility even with compatibilizers in certain samples.
- **Reduced Elongation:** Significant reductions in elongation at break were observed in samples containing compatibilizers.
- **Thermal and Mechanical Variability:** High variability in thermal and mechanical properties depending on specific compositions.
- **Industrial Scale Testing Required:** These advancements still need to be tested at an industrial scale to evaluate their commercial viability.

3.6. ADVANCES IN ENZYMATIC TREATMENT

This section addresses the advancements in enzymatic recycling of PE/PET plastic sheets (non-aluminized) obtained through delamination (Section 3.4). It focuses on enzyme engineering (PETase and PEase) to break down these plastics into their base monomers, facilitating their valorization and preventing their usual disposal in landfills.

Results Achieved:

- PETase: A sixfold increase in enzymatic activity was achieved using directed evolution methods, advanced computational design, and machine learning. A protocol was also developed for the recovery of products such as TPA and EG, scaling reactions to 100 g.
- PEase: The initial enzyme was not viable for industrial use, leading to the design of a *de novo* enzyme. Although a stable and promising design was achieved, the required activity levels for PE have not yet been reached.
- The improved PETase activity was evaluated on pretreated PET samples and PE/PET bilaminates. It was concluded that bilaminate layers are unsuitable for this type of enzymatic recycling.
- The enzymatic depolymerization reaction was scaled up to a 1 L reactor, achieving high-purity product recovery through ultrafiltration.

Limitations and Next Steps:

- Integrating PEase at an industrial level remains a challenge due to low activity in the initial variants.

- The incompatibility of PE/PET bilaminates with enzymatic depolymerization.
- The thermal stability of the improved PETase still requires optimization for commercialization.

3.7. ADVANCES IN ALUMINIUM MODIFICATION

The described process aims to enhance compatibility between aluminium particles (obtained through the delamination process) and polymer matrices, particularly in hydrophobic polymers such as HDPE and PP. The main challenge lies in the fact that aluminium particles are typically hydrophilic due to the passivated oxide layer on their surface, while the polymers into which they are incorporated are hydrophobic. This disparity causes dispersion issues, negatively affecting the mechanical, optical, and barrier properties of the materials. To address this problem, the proposed process modifies aluminium particles with a polyisobutylene (PIB) shell, improving their compatibility and dispersion within the polymer matrix. The key stages of this process are outlined below.

- Obtaining Aluminium Particles: Aluminium particles are recovered from multilayer materials with aluminium barriers. These particles are obtained through a separation technology developed by the partner Saperatec, which produces pure aluminium particles in both nanometric and micrometric sizes.
- Treatment of Aluminium Particles: Aluminium surfaces oxidize in air, forming a passivated layer containing -OH groups. To increase the quantity of these groups, the aluminium particles are treated with hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) at high temperatures, facilitating the formation of chemical bonds with suitable groups (e.g., acid, silane, or phosphate) in subsequent stages.
- Controlled Synthesis of Polyisobutylene (PIB): PIB is synthesized via controlled cationic polymerization to produce a polymer with a specific molecular weight and

low polydispersity. The process utilizes appropriate initiators (such as TMPCl) and reaction conditions to achieve high-quality PIB.

- Modification of PIB Chain Ends: During the PIB synthesis process, the polymer's chain end is modified through a Friedel-Crafts alkylation reaction using compounds like (3-aminopropyl)ethoxysilane (APTES). This introduces reactive groups into PIB, enabling its binding to the surface of aluminium particles.
- Grafting of PIB onto Aluminium Particles: Pre-treated aluminium particles are chemically modified with functionalized PIB (via APTES) through a grafting reaction, forming covalent bonds between PIB and the aluminium surface. This step ensures that the aluminium particles are coated with a PIB shell, enhancing their dispersion in the polymer matrix.
- Evaluation of Dispersion and Material Properties: PIB-modified aluminium particles are dispersed in polymers such as HDPE or PP. The resulting composite materials are evaluated for mechanical, optical, and barrier properties, aiming for significant improvements compared to materials containing unmodified aluminium particles.

Results Achieved:

- Successfully modified aluminium particles with a polyisobutylene (PIB) shell, improving their dispersibility in organic solvents and hydrophobic polymers like HDPE or PP, enhancing their compatibility with polymer matrices.
- Surface modification of aluminium through H_2O_2 treatment, followed by PIB modification using APTES, rendered the treated aluminium particles hydrophobic, improving their dispersion in polymeric materials.

- Achieved controlled PIB synthesis with a low polydispersity index using TMPCl as an initiator, creating PIB with appropriate molecular weight for modifying aluminium particles.
- The composites produced were optically homogeneous and the mechanical properties did not change in direct comparison to PP materials without fillers.
- A process has been developed in which commercially available PIB can also be used directly for the successful modification of aluminium particles (e.g. KOMAD ADDITIVE). This makes successful realization - even on a large scale - possible and probable.
- The developed method can be transferred directly to other (nano-)particle systems, e.g. aluminium oxide, clay and various oxides.

Limitations and Next Steps:

- Size of aluminium particles need to be more homogenous and better controlled (smaller particles)
- Variation of PIB (synthesis or commercially) not easy to achieve
- Optimization of barrier properties is low in comparison to eg aluminium-films

3.8. ORGANIC BY-PRODUCTS RECOVERY AND MICROPLASTIC REMOVAL

This section focuses on evaluating and developing technologies for treating wastewater generated during the washing of plastics in the pre-treatment phase. Two main technologies were investigated: **ultrafiltration membrane filtration** and **electrocoagulation**. The objectives were to remove contaminants such as microplastics and organic matter from the

wastewater while exploring the reuse of the organic fraction for the production of bioplastics (PHA).

Additionally, a pilot system was designed to test these technologies under conditions closer to real-world operations. The trials included chemical analyses of the wash water, evaluation of contaminant removal efficiency, and the feasibility of implementing these processes in a closed-loop system.

Results Achieved:

- Both technologies effectively removed microplastics, significantly reducing potential contamination before the water could be discharged or reused.
- Part of the dissolved organic matter in the water was successfully recovered, with potential reuse as a raw material for bioplastic (PHA) production, promoting process sustainability.
- A pilot system was designed and adapted to assess the performance of these technologies under conditions resembling industrial environments.
- Electrocoagulation proved particularly effective at removing turbidity and water color, as well as separating the organic fraction into distinct layers (upper or lower), facilitating handling.
- Pilot-scale ultrafiltration tests confirmed that with appropriate flow rates, permeate rates could be increased without significantly compromising process efficiency.
- The tested technologies demonstrated their potential to advance toward closed-loop systems, minimizing water waste and reducing environmental contamination.

Limitations and Next Steps:

- A tendency for membranes to foul requires regular cleaning, which could increase operational costs.
- Current electrocoagulation equipment does not allow for adequate collection of separated solids, limiting their recovery potential. Moreover, it adds either iron or aluminium hydroxides to the water, which might be limiting the reuse potential for

PHA production as they might be toxic. Additionally, both technologies remove the pollutants from the water, but they are collected in a waste stream. In WP6, an strategy for the valorization of the by-product, including water reuse, will be studied.

4 . Conclusions

The Agro2Circular project has made significant progress in overcoming the technical challenges of recycling agro-food and agricultural plastics, which have a multi-layer structure and are contaminated with agrochemicals and organic waste. The developed technologies, such as washing, optical sorting, delamination of aluminium fractions, and enzymatic modification of plastics, have proven highly effective in separating and decontaminating these complex materials. These processes have enabled the recovery of high-value-added recycled plastics, such as non-aluminized plastic fractions and modified aluminium. In the latter case, an innovative method has been developed to modify (nano)particles of (oxide) aluminium with a hydrophobic shell, improving their compatibility with hydrophobic polymers to obtain composites with improved properties. Additionally, organic products derived from wastewater treatment have been successfully recovered.

Now, in Work Package 6 (WP6), the next crucial step will be to scale these advances from the laboratory to a pilot scale. In this new phase, an online pilot-scale demonstrator will be implemented, allowing the validation and evaluation of the developed processes and technologies under real-world conditions. This demonstrator will focus on optimizing the efficiency and industrial feasibility of the technological solutions, enabling the assessment of their performance, scalability, and commercial viability in a large-scale production environment.

